

OFDM-Based Underwater Visible Light Communication

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Abstract—Underwater visible light communication (UVLC) offers a high-speed and low-latency alternative to traditional underwater data transmission methods such as acoustic and radio frequency systems, which face inherent limitations in aquatic environments. This letter presents the design and implementation of an orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM)-based UVLC system using multi-order quadrature amplitude modulation (M-QAM) with a focus on reliable performance in real-world conditions. Experiments were conducted in three water conditions—clear, murky, and dynamically turbid—using a 545 nm LED. The results show that 64-QAM provides stable performance across all conditions, while higher-order schemes, such as 128-QAM and 256-QAM, offer increased data rates but suffer from higher bit error rates under turbidity. The study demonstrates that the proposed system can maintain short-range high-throughput communication in variable underwater environments.

Index Terms—Bit error rate, orthogonal frequency division multiplexing, underwater wireless communication, visible light communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

UNDERWATER environments present both significant challenges and promising opportunities for communication technologies. Traditional methods, such as acoustic and radio frequency (RF) systems, face inherent limitations. RF suffers from high attenuation and limited propagation distance underwater, while acoustic technologies, despite their longer range, are constrained by low data transmission rates and vulnerability to interference and reflections [3]. These limitations have driven the exploration of alternative solutions, including visible light communication (VLC).

VLC uses modulated light sources, such as blue and green light-emitting diodes (LEDs), which are optimal for underwater applications due to their reduced attenuation in water at wavelengths between 450 and 550 nm. This enables VLC to achieve high data rates, up to several gigabits per second, over short distances, making it ideal for applications requiring fast and reliable communication [4], [5]. Applications include

monitoring diver health, environmental observation of the seabed, and underwater drone operations [6].

A unique advantage of underwater VLC (UVLC) is its directional line-of-sight (LoS) communication capability, which minimizes interference in crowded underwater environments, such as harbors. Unlike acoustic signals that propagate omnidirectionally, UVLC can deliver highly targeted signals to specific receivers, thereby improving link reliability in terms of reduced interference and lower bit error rate (BER) [7]. However, UVLC also faces challenges related to the physical and chemical properties of water, including turbidity, suspended particles, and microorganisms that affect light absorption and scattering. Advanced modulation techniques and performance optimization methods are being developed to address these issues and maximize the transmission efficiency [8].

Recent research efforts in the field of UVLC have focused on enhancing data rate, link stability, and robustness against environmental challenges such as scattering, turbulence, and misalignment. Various studies have explored device-level improvements, system-level architectures, and signal-processing strategies to overcome the inherent limitations of underwater optical propagation. For instance, Wang et al. [9] presented a vertical-structure gallium nitride (GaN) LED designed specifically for UVLC applications, aiming to improve both light extraction efficiency and modulation bandwidth. Their study involved the design and fabrication of a sub-wavelength GaN LED, achieving a transmission rate of 10 Mbps under non-return-to-zero (NRZ) on-off keying (OOK) modulation across a 60 cm underwater link. To further enhance communication reliability, Sutradhar et al. [10] investigated a camera-assisted UVLC system that integrates LED localization and computer vision tracking to mitigate BER and packet error rate (PER). Their experimental analysis showed that active tracking of the transmitter significantly reduces signal loss and improves BER/PER performance, particularly under obstruction or motion-induced misalignment. Without tracking, both BER and PER increase rapidly in such conditions, whereas the implementation of tracking reduces PER to 25% at 400 kHz over a 20 cm underwater link, demonstrating the potential of hybrid optical-vision techniques in dynamic environments. Moreover, Lv et al. [11] proposed a total reflection-based UVLC system utilizing InGaN-based micro-LEDs at the air-water interface, addressing challenges associated with dynamic marine conditions. Their experiments revealed that a total reflection angle of 7° enables a BER of 3.10×10^{-3} for transmission distances up to 180 cm when using an avalanche photodiode (APD) receiver. These results confirm

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Preprint of a first version of this study can be found on Authorea [1]. The data used in this study are available through the Zenodo repository [2].

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the feasibility of non-line-of-sight (NLoS) communication, providing an effective alternative when conventional LoS links are disrupted by surface disturbances or turbidity variations.

The future of UVLC lies in its integration with other technologies, such as acoustic systems and sonar sensors, to create hybrid communication systems. These hybrid approaches can take advantage of the long-range capabilities of acoustic signals alongside the high-speed transmission of VLC, covering a wide spectrum of underwater applications [12]. However, most experimental studies focus on static turbidity models. There is a limited understanding of how particle movement and water currents—typical in real-world scenarios—affect the stability of multi-state quadrature amplitude modulation (M-QAM) constellations in orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM)-based UVLC.

The main contributions of this letter include:

- Experimental assessment of the robustness of OFDM-based UVLC under dynamic turbidity conditions using a custom-built testbed with active water circulation. Unlike static attenuation tests, this setup replicates signal fluctuations caused by suspended particle movement.
- Analysis of the trade-off between spectral efficiency (data rate) and link stability (BER) for different QAM orders in dynamic environments, identifying the practical limits of higher-order modulation in turbid water.

The rest of the letter is organized as follows. Section II describes the theoretical model with the proposed system (experimental platform and hardware trade-offs) for our experiment. Section III compares the experiment results. The experimental scenarios consisted of tests to measure the BER and transmission rates under various water conditions. Section IV discusses the results of the experiments and provides a comparison with related works. The last Section V concludes with a proposal for future work on UVLC communication.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Theoretical Model

The proposed UVLC system employs intensity modulation/direct detection (IM/DD) using OFDM. The received optical power P_{rx} in an underwater channel is governed by the LoS path loss model and the attenuation properties of the water. The DC channel gain $H(0)$ is given by the Lambertian radiation pattern [13]:

$$H(0) = \frac{(m+1)A_{det}}{2\pi d^2} \cos^m(\phi) T_s(\psi) g(\psi) \cos(\psi), \quad (1)$$

where A_{det} is the physical area of the photodetector, d is the transmission distance, ϕ is the angle of irradiance, and ψ is the angle of incidence. The Lambertian order m is related to the transmitter semi-angle $\Phi_{1/2}$ by $m = -\ln(2)/\ln(\cos \Phi_{1/2})$. $T_s(\psi)$ and $g(\psi)$ represent the gain of the optical filter and the concentrator, respectively. In the underwater environment, the optical signal undergoes absorption and scattering, described by Beer-Lambert's law. The received power is thus expressed as:

$$P_{rx} = P_{tx} H(0) \exp(-c(\lambda)d), \quad (2)$$

where P_{tx} is the transmitted optical power and $c(\lambda)$ is the beam attenuation coefficient, which is the sum of absorption (a) and scattering (b) coefficients ($c(\lambda) = a(\lambda) + b(\lambda)$). The transmitted OFDM signal $x(t)$ is generated by modulating the subcarriers with M-QAM symbols X_k . To ensure a real-valued output required for IM/DD, Hermitian symmetry is applied to the subcarriers before the inverse Fast Fourier transform (IFFT):

$$x(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X_k e^{j2\pi k \Delta f t}, \quad (3)$$

where N is the number of subcarriers and Δf is the subcarrier spacing. A cyclic prefix (CP) is appended to $x(t)$ to mitigate inter-symbol interference (ISI) caused by multipath scattering in the turbid water channel.

B. Experimental Setup

The entire system is based on virtual instrumentation and is implemented in LabVIEW Communications by Emerson. The proposed system serves as an OFDM transceiver and uses M-QAM to modulate individual subcarriers. The system begins by generating a pseudorandom sequence of 125 bits, which is then mapped onto symbols according to M-QAM modulation. This results in 625 symbols that are divided into 5 sets, each containing 125 symbols, with additional pilot carriers inserted for frequency correction. The total number of subcarriers used in the OFDM system is 256, ensuring compatibility with the IFFT process. While simpler schemes such as OOK with Manchester coding are commonly recommended (as per IEEE 802.15.7 [14]), our study employs M-QAM due to its higher spectral efficiency and adaptability in turbid conditions. The higher data rates achievable with M-QAM also align with the increasing demand for real-time communication. Fig. 1 presents a block diagram of the testing setup, which remained consistent throughout all measurements. In this work, we focus on the measurement of the BER as well as the achievable bit rate. Four SAMSUNG 3LED SMD2835 modules with IP68 protection were used as a light source. Each LED emitted light in the spectrum of 545 nm. Each module had a power consumption of 1.2 W.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the measured system.

On the receiving side was a Thorlabs PDA100A2 photodetector with an active area of 75.4 mm^2 placed directly opposite the center of the light source. An automatic gain control system was not employed in this setup. Instead, the selection of the appropriate QAM order was guided by a BER threshold of 10^{-3} , a standard criterion in VLC systems, ensuring acceptable performance under varying conditions. In the graphical results, this threshold is referred to as the forward error correction (FEC) limit. The photodetector was placed externally against the aquarium wall to avoid immersion. The LED transmitter was completely submerged underwater and shines directly on the photodetector. The LED module was placed at the maximum distance of 55 cm from the photodetector. The photodetector also allows a variable gain setting of 0–70 dB. However, as the gain increases, the usable effective bandwidth decreases [15]. On the transmitting side, a shielded and highly-linear Mini-Circuits ZX60-100VH+ amplifier was used to amplify the universal software radio peripheral (USRP) RF signal, providing a gain of 36 dB and a maximum output of 1 W. Its operating frequency range is 0.3–100 MHz. On the receiving side, a shielded low-noise Mini-Circuits ZFL-1000LN+ amplifier was used to amplify the received signal from the photodetector by 20 dB. Its operating frequency range is 0.1–1000 MHz. Both amplifiers were also equipped with a capacitor to eliminate interference from the local grid. A Bias Tee was used to sum the transmitted high-frequency signal (RF input) supplied from the USRP and the DC signal from the source (DC input). The result was a signal (RF+DC) that oscillated around the DC level of the signal from the source, which can modulate a portion of the optical signal. A customized USRP 2954R [16] software-defined radio (SDR) was used as a transmitting and receiving element. The experimental evaluation was conducted in a 55 cm long aquarium under three distinct scenarios: (i) clear tap water serving as a baseline; (ii) static murky water, created by adding fine soil and organic sediment to simulate natural turbidity; and (iii) turbid water, where a submersible jet pump induced water circulation and turbulence. The measurements were performed using a base carrier frequency of 1 MHz and a bandwidth of 800 kHz. The link performance was evaluated for 64-QAM, 128-QAM, and 256-QAM schemes over transmission distances ranging from 15 cm to 55 cm in 5 cm increments. The setup for the clean water scenario is depicted in Fig. 2

Fig. 2. Photos taken during measurement with a clean water setup.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND SCENARIO RESULTS

All experiments were designed to be as close as possible to the real conditions that can occur in a natural water environment, whether it is clear water (saltwater or freshwater), murky water with settled sediment, or turbid murky water with commonly occurring currents.

Fig. 3 presents a comparison of the modulation formats across varying distances in static environments (clear vs. murky water). Trendlines based on quadratic regression are included to illustrate the degradation characteristics. For 64-QAM, 128-QAM, and 256-QAM, a strictly monotonic deterioration of BER is observed as turbidity increases. Specifically, for 256-QAM in murky water, the BER exceeds the FEC threshold of 10^{-3} at approximately 40 cm. In contrast, 64-QAM demonstrates robust performance, maintaining BER values well below the FEC limit even at the maximum measured distance of 55 cm, indicating a higher resilience to turbidity compared to higher-order modulation schemes.

Fig. 3. Comparison of BER in clean water and murky water. Carrier frequency 1 MHz, bandwidth 800 kHz.

Fig. 4 illustrates the impact of dynamic conditions (turbid water with a jet pump) compared to the stable murky baseline. To address the signal fluctuations inherent to dynamic underwater channels, 95% prediction intervals (shaded regions) have been added to the regression models. Unlike the stable environment, the results for 64-QAM and 128-QAM in turbid water exhibit noticeable variance. These deviations are attributed to the stochastic nature of the optical path, where turbulence and moving particles cause random temporal fading and scintillation. The occasional improvement in BER at specific distances suggests momentarily clearer optical paths between the transmitter and receiver, while degradations correspond to beam obstruction by particle clusters or air bubbles.

The prediction intervals in Fig. 4 confirm that these fluctuations are within the expected statistical bounds of the dynamic channel. While 256-QAM showed less variance in this specific dataset, the overall trend confirms that dynamic turbidity introduces significant instability compared to static conditions. These findings underscore the necessity for robust equalization algorithms to mitigate rapid channel variations. Future research should extend to larger water volumes and realistic environments incorporating natural flora and uneven scattering surfaces.

Fig. 4. Comparison of BER in murky water and turbid water with a jet pump. Carrier frequency 1 MHz, bandwidth 800 kHz.

Fig. 5 shows photos taken during the measurements in still murky water with settled branches and leaves, and in murky water with a water pump to simulate a real environment.

Fig. 5. (a) Measurement of still murky water, and (b) water with a jet pump for turbidity.

The achievable raw data rates (R_b) were derived based on the specific OFDM frame structure defined by the system parameters, following the principles of optical OFDM [17]. The frame consists of $N_{FFT} = 256$ subcarriers, containing 106 null guard subcarriers (53 on each side) and 25 pilot tones for synchronization, resulting in $N_{data} = 125$ effective data-carrying subcarriers. With a CP of $N_{CP} = 64$ samples and a bandwidth of $B = 800$ kHz, the data rate is calculated as:

$$R_b = \frac{N_{data}}{N_{FFT} + N_{CP}} \cdot B \cdot \log_2(M). \quad (4)$$

Based on this configuration, the theoretical raw data rates correspond to 1.875 Mbit/s for 64-QAM, 2.188 Mbit/s for 128-QAM, and 2.500 Mbit/s for 256-QAM. These values establish the theoretical throughput limits used for the trade-off analysis.

IV. DISCUSSION

UVLC is increasingly recognized as a promising alternative for high-bandwidth short-range data transfer in aquatic environments. Although conventional RF and acoustic methods often grapple with limited bandwidth or high latency, VLC capitalizes on the relatively favorable optical properties of water, provided that factors such as turbidity are properly managed.

A reference measurement was first conducted under conditions that approximate an empty aquarium. The results were

nearly identical to those obtained in clear water. This is consistent with theoretical models, as the optical attenuation of clear water over short distances (<1 m) is negligible (<0.2 dB) compared to geometric loss [18].

Subsequent tests were carried out in turbid water, covering both saltwater and freshwater environments. In particular, the measured BER values remained comparable between turbid saltwater and turbid freshwater, indicating that suspended particles and turbulent flow are the main contributors to signal degradation. This aligns with the physical channel properties demonstrated in [19], which established that scattering from suspended particles severely degrades the received optical power, whereas the impact of salinity variations on signal attenuation is comparatively minor. Our BER measurements practically reflect this dominant scattering effect.

Our UVLC system employs OFDM with QAM subcarriers, diverging from many recent studies that rely on OOK and its variants. While OOK is favored for its hardware implementation simplicity, single-carrier schemes are highly susceptible to ISI at high bit rates due to the limited modulation bandwidth of commercial LEDs and the dispersive nature of the underwater channel [20]. In contrast, multi-carrier schemes, such as OFDM, effectively mitigate ISI through the use of a CP. Consequently, concerning spectral efficiency and robustness in band-limited UVLC systems, OFDM generally performs better than OOK, allowing for higher data rates [21]–[23]. Although higher-order QAM is inherently more sensitive to SNR degradation than binary schemes, our findings demonstrate that with appropriate channel equalization 64-QAM-based OFDM maintains stable communication even under dynamic turbidity. This positions the proposed system as a spectrally efficient alternative to OOK for high-throughput short-range applications, where maximizing the data rate is prioritized over hardware simplicity.

Fig. 6 shows the average BER values with standard deviation error bars for three modulation schemes (64-QAM, 128-QAM, 256-QAM) across three scenarios: clear water, static murky water, and turbid water with an active jet pump. The results indicate a clear trade-off between spectral efficiency and link robustness. 64-QAM exhibits the lowest BER across all conditions, remaining well below the FEC limit of 10^{-3} . This stability is attributed to the larger Euclidean distance between constellation points, making the symbol decision less sensitive to the scattering-induced SNR degradation. Conversely, 256-QAM, while offering the highest theoretical throughput of 2.500 Mbit/s (compared to 1.875 Mbit/s for 64-QAM and 2.188 Mbit/s for 128-QAM), suffers significantly in degraded environments. As shown in Fig. 6, the average BER for 256-QAM exceeds the 10^{-3} threshold in both murky and turbid scenarios, rendering it unreliable for practical deployment without heavy error correction overhead.

Notably, the transition from clean to murky water introduces the most substantial BER increase due to static scattering. The subsequent transition to the dynamic turbid scenario (active pump) results in larger variance in the error rate, as indicated by the extended error bars, particularly for higher-order modulations. This suggests that while the average attenuation remains comparable to the static murky case, the

Fig. 6. Average BER values for all three modulation schemes in all scenarios. Carrier frequency 1 MHz, bandwidth 800 kHz.

particle movement introduces rapid channel fluctuations that destabilize the dense 256-QAM constellation.

To quantify the impact of BER on the actual system performance, we analyzed the relationship between the raw data rate (R_b) and the effective throughput (R_{eff}). The effective throughput can be estimated as $R_{eff} \approx R_b \cdot (1 - PER)$ [24], where PER represents the probability of a frame containing at least one bit error. Assuming a frame length of L bits, PER is derived from BER as $PER = 1 - (1 - BER)^L$. For 256-QAM in turbid conditions, the high raw data rate of 2.500 Mbit/s is negated by a BER of $\approx 4 \times 10^{-3}$. With a frame size of $L \approx 1000$ bits, the probability of a successful packet transmission drops below 2%, resulting in a near-zero effective throughput. In contrast, 64-QAM ($R_b = 1.875$ Mbit/s) maintains a BER of $\approx 10^{-4}$, ensuring a packet success rate of over 90% and preserving a stable effective throughput. This demonstrates that in dynamic turbidity, lower-order modulation schemes offer superior reliability despite their lower theoretical capacity.

V. CONCLUSION

This letter has demonstrated the feasibility of an OFDM-based UVLC system using M-QAM modulation for short-range underwater communication under various environmental conditions. Experimental results confirmed that higher-order modulation schemes, such as 256-QAM, can achieve significantly higher data rates in clear water, whereas 64-QAM consistently exhibited greater resilience under challenging conditions, such as turbidity and induced water currents. Despite the presence of suspended particles and dynamic flow, stable data transmission was achieved over distances up to 55 cm, particularly with the 128-QAM scheme. These findings validate the potential of carefully designed OFDM UVLC systems as a viable alternative to conventional acoustic or RF-based methods, particularly in controlled or moderately adverse aquatic environments. Future research will explore deployment in larger and more complex underwater environments, including natural obstructions and biologically diverse ecosystems, and will further develop adaptive equalization techniques to improve robustness in real-time dynamic conditions.

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